

Analysis on Achievement Motivation and Academic Engagement of Adolescent Students with Exam Anxiety

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ABSTRACT

Exam anxiety and performance on examinations are the focus of this research among school pupils. His study will use a quantitative approach to research, and the questions that will be asked about it will be phrased in a general way. In order to carry out this study, we will make use of a method known as systematic random sampling, and the data will be gathered through the use of questionnaires. The respondents consist of a total of five hundred young people currently enrolled in schools. Information collected for this study have analysed using SPSS, a statistical programme designed specifically for social science research.

1. Introduction

The anxiety and tension that characterise examination phobia may have their origins in the anticipation and performance of examinations [1]. The students regularly report feeling that they could be losing control and that something major has gone wrong. You're experiencing physical symptoms that are very comparable to serious health issues, and in some cases, you may even feel as though death or some other terrible catastrophe is imminent [9]. Anxiety is a normal human feeling that is a part of being alive and may be a good source of adrenaline in certain situations. However, for a select few, adrenaline can surge to levels much beyond the norm, with potentially disastrous results [2-4]. It regularly hear the terms "exam fever" and "exam anxiety" used to describe the feeling of being overly prepared for a test. According to studies in psychology, this is a symptom of anxiety [5].

Hypothesis

- (1) Stress over exams will likely have a favourable effect on how well you do.
- (2) More women than men would report feeling nervous before an exam.
- (3) It is expected that students' post-treatment performance in mathematics would be higher than their pre-treatment performance since cognitive restructuring and relaxation strategies are beneficial in lowering anxiety and depression and enhancing test performance.
- (4) The combination of cognitive restructuring and deep breathing relaxation treatment would improve the academic performance of students compared to both the control group and the deep breathing relaxation therapy only group.

2. Review of Literature

A more stable and confident person is reequipped to handle anxiety and convert it into something very productive [7]. The ability to deal efficiently with anxiety is one of the prime considerations for players. Each athlete must learn to cope with the anxiety involved in their career [8]. The various behavioral patterns indicating anxiety are

rather desperate and are often hard to recognize, according to Jyoti Singh (2020) [1]. Procrastinating students were shown to have worse time management, more self-doubt and illogical views about studying, and lower academic achievement and well-being than their non-procrastinating peers C. Atalayin, M. Balkis, H. Tezel, and G. Kayrak (2018) [4].

2.1. Analysis-related statistical methods and tools

The data that had been obtained had previously been analysed with the assistance of relevant statistical techniques. Both the goals of the study and the characteristics of the data that were going to be analysed had a role in the decision-making process for the statistical methods that were going to be used [10-13]. The method known as WEIGHTED MEAN was utilised in the conduct of this research.

Weighted mean = $\frac{\sum wx}{\sum w}$ Σ = summation (or, in other words, just add them all together) is a straight-forward representation of this formula. A weight, denoted by w, represents these values.

2.2. Limitations of the study

- ✗ The research was conducted with just 500 participants who responded to the questionnaire.
- ✗ The researcher was only able to perform the study during school hours because it was the only time the school was open.
- ✗ The outcomes that were highlighted were during the time period of the investigation.
- ✗ Only students in secondary schools participated in the research; primary school students, students in higher education institutions, or college students were excluded.
- ✗ Due to the fact that the findings and conclusions of this study were derived from information gathered from high school students during data collection.
- ✗ The approach that was taken and the instruments that were used in the analysis of the data each had specific advantages and disadvantages of their own, and they also mirrored the restrictions that were placed on the database.

Table 1. Exam anxiety coping mechanisms

S.No.	Statements	Average Mean	Interpretation
1.	I calm down few minutes before exam to make my mind free from anxiety.	3.46	Agree
2.	I am Rereading the answers I gave on the test before turning it in.	3.88	Agree
3.	I am Discussing my approaching test with friends a few weeks before the test.	3.69	Agree
4.	I am Sitting down to study before a regularly scheduled class.	3.62	Agree

5.	Reviewing study materials the night before an exam.	3.64	Agree
6.	Discovering I need an A or B on the next exam to pass the course.	3.83	Agree
7.	I take prior action to try to get rid of Exam anxiety.	3.73	Agree
8.	Making an appointment to see the teacher regarding some course problem.	3.70	Agree
9.	I see exam in a different light, to make it seem more positive.	3.06	Neutral
10.	I spent additional time to prepare for difficult exams.	3.33	Neutral
11.	I clarify my doubts to avoid tough situations during exam.	3.12	Neutral
12.	I try to come up with some strategies to face exam confidently.	3.94	Agree
13.	I prevent other things interfering with my efforts at dealing with exam.	4.09	Agree
14.	I do combine studies to overcome exam unease with my friends.	3.83	Agree
15.	I Prepare exams by using frequent short study sessions.	4.40	Strongly Agree
16.	I Avoid last minute studying to prevent tense.	2.84	Neutral
17.	I Reward myself when I finished with the exam.	2.99	Neutral
18.	I eat well during the day of the exam, preferably something nutritious.	2.30	Disagree

2.3. Recommendations

- ✗ The students should refrain from reading new answers the night before the exam and instead review the answers that they have already learned.
- ✗ Students are required to anticipate difficult questions on each and every test, and they should arrange their responses properly in order to do well without feeling unduly stressed.
- ✗ Becoming a tutor is an activity that may be enriching, inspiring, and powerful, thus it is best for kids who do well in school to choose this career path. It will lead to an increase in general knowledge across the board.
- ✗ Reviewing for the examination is a really beneficial exercise. However, students shouldn't continue to examine the materials in the ten minutes leading up to the start of the exam.
- ✗ It is important for parents not to put undue pressure on their children to study for tests. Instead of doing that, they might teach students how to deal with the stress of exams.
- ✗ It is important that each and every student has the chance to discuss their academic concerns with their respective professors and other authorities.

- ✗ It is the responsibility of teachers to assist pupils in developing a timetable for studying.
- ✗ If the students are able to learn how to control their levels of test anxiety, then they will have a useful tool for improving their academic achievement.

3. The Findings and Implications of the Study

All humans experience anxiety, as this study demonstrates. Most students think they may improve their performance by focusing on their worries, but research shows that this is not the case. Reduced productivity among the remaining respondents is a direct result of their anxiety. If students get effective counselling, they may be able to channel their anxiety toward academic success.

Declarations

Source of Funding

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Competing Interests Statement

The author declares no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The author declares that he/she consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The author is willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

References

- [1] Jyoti Singh (2020). Comparative study of pre-competitive anxiety in physical education students of higher and senior secondary schools. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 8(10).
- [2] Nancy, W.M. Gichohi (2019). Influence of Anxiety on Academic Performance among Students at The Technical University of Kenya. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Volume 9.
- [3] Alia J. Crum (2017). The role of stress mindset in shaping cognitive, emotional, and physiological responses to challenging and threatening stress. *An International Journal*, 30(4).
- [4] C. Atalayin, M. Balkis H. Tezel, and G. Kayrak (2018). Procrastination and predictor variables among a group of dental students in Turkey. *Psychology Health and Medicine*, 23(6): 726–732.
- [5] Dryden, W., & Sabelus, S. (2012). The perceived credibility of two rational emotive behavior therapy rationales for the treatment of academic procrastination. *J. of Rational-E-motive & Cognitive-Behavior Therapy*, 30(1): 1–24.
- [6] Poulomee Datta (2014). *International journal of special education Australian Catholic University Test anxiety research: students with vision impairments and students with mild intellectual disabilities*, 29(2).
- [7] Neemati N, Hooshangi R, Shurideh A. (2014). An investigation into the learners' attitudes towards factors affecting their exam performance: a case from Razi university. *Procedia Soc Behav Sci.*, 98: 1331–1339.

- [8] Bharati Roy (2013). Test anxiety and academic Performance of School Students. *International Journal of Sci Research*, 2(1).
- [9] Archana kumari (2014). Examination stress and anxiety: A study of college students. *Global Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(1).
- [10] Mohammad Ahsan & Anand Kumar (2016). A Study of the Relationship between Test Anxiety and Study Habits of Physical Education Students, *International Journal of Sports and Physical Education*, 2(3).
- [11] S. Zacks & M. Hen (2018). Academic interventions for academic procrastination: a review of the literature. *Journal of Prevention and Intervention in the Community*, 46(2): 117–130.
- [12] Swaminathan, Bharathi, & Ananth Kumar Tamilarasan (2021). Mental Health Decline During Corona Virus Outbreak. In *Sustainability Measures for COVID-19 Pandemic*, Pages 135-155, Springer, Singapore.
- [13] Ananth, Christo, Stalin Jacob, Jenifer Darling Rosita, M. S. Muthuraman, & T. Ananth Kumar. (2022). Low Cost Visual Support System for Challenged People. In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Smart Technologies and Systems for Next Generation Computing (ICSTSN)*, Pages 1-4.